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DESIGNING ECO-FRIENDLY ALTERNATIVE TO THE MAGNESIA-CHROMITE AGGREGATES

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ABSTRACT

Due to its outstanding thermomechanical and corrosive performance, electrofused magnesia-chromite aggregates (EMCA) have been consistently applied to refractory compositions since the beginning of the 20th century. Notwithstanding the performance of refractories containing this raw material, the rising environmental and safety concerns have been driving the replacement of chrome-containing compositions by greener alternatives as this type of refractory can generate a highly toxic by-product (Cr^{6+}), suppressing landfilling and recycling. However, finding eco-friendly and affordable alternatives to EMCA remains a challenge. Firstly, there is a lack of understanding of the mechanisms that give rise to its good performance and, secondly, conventional formulation criteria can hardly account for the microstructure complexity of this raw material. In this work, multiple electron-microscope-based techniques, such as EBSD and EDS, were used to assess EMCA microstructural features and a mechanism to explain their generation was proposed. Based on the latter and with the aid of thermodynamic calculations, the concepts of designing compositionally complex ceramics were applied to find eco-friendly alternatives to EMCA. From the 154 simulated systems, the 4 most promising compositions were experimentally produced and characterized at a laboratory scale. Although kinetics aspects still must be addressed, Cr-free EMCA mimetized microstructures were obtained, highlighting that this design approach can be used to support the development of novel raw-material that can better merge performance, cost and eco-friendliness.

INTRODUCTION

The search for refractory systems capable of withstanding the complex solicitations (e.g. thermal shock, corrosion, erosion) is a constant demand in high-temperature industries¹. To address such a scenario, refractories containing electrofused magnesia-chromium aggregates (EMCA) have been broadly applied since the 1960s¹. In these systems, which fit into the compositionally complex ceramic classification¹, the predominant phases are periclase and a solid solution based on a complex spinel obtained by combining different types of spinel structures (AB_2O_4 -type phases, in which A represents a divalent cation and B a trivalent one)². This complex structure results in excellent resistance to corrosion and slag penetration². Additionally, although the literature does not report in detail the driving force for this phenomenon, the high number of preferentially oriented microcracks formed on the EMCA microstructure gives rise to a material with good flexibility and thermal shock damage resistance.

Besides its outstanding corrosion and thermal shock damage resistance, EMCA has received little attention from the scientific community in recent decades, which can be attributed to its toxicity (mainly due to the formation of hexavalent chromium). Thus, greater efforts have been made to study safer systems, especially based on MgAl_2O_4 , as alternatives to replace EMCA, but equivalent performance in applications such as in RH degassers has not yet been achieved³. Consequently, there is a lack of understanding of the mechanisms that lead to EMCA properties, especially related to its high thermal shock damage resistance.

Aiming at understanding the mechanism that leads to their features, multiple techniques were used in this work to assess the microstructure of commercially-available EMCA. Based on that and using thermodynamic calculations (CALPHAD), the concepts of designing compositionally complex ceramics⁴ were applied to find eco-friendly alternatives to this chromium-containing raw material. Some of the most promising compositions were then processed by electrofusion in lab-scale arc furnace equipment and their resulting microstructures were analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Microstructural characterization was firstly conducted for commercially-available electrofused magnesia-chromium aggregates (FMCR 18-20, $d_{50} = 3$ mm, Chenglong, Liaoyang, China). The as-received samples were embedded in a polymeric resin, cut to expose their sectioned surface, ground using SiC-based sandpaper, and polished in AutoMet (model Phoenix Beta, Buehler, USA) using polycrystalline diamond paste with particle sizes ranging from 15 μm to 0.25 μm (MetaDi Medium Concentration, Buehler, USA). The diamond-polished samples had their microstructure assessed by backscattered electrons imaging (BSE) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) on a scanning electron microscope device (Inspect S50, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). To avoid charging artefacts, the latter analysis was conducted on golden-coated surfaces (Balzers SCD 004, Bal-Tec, Switzerland). The crystallographic orientation of the EMCA phases was assessed by electron backscattered diffraction technique (30 kV, Inspec S50, FEI, USA). Thermodynamic calculations were carried out in Equilib module of FactSage software (FToxid and FactPS databases, version 6.4, CRCT, Canada) using the EMCA chemical composition (X-ray fluorescence, MagiX PRO, Malvern Panalytical, UK) to assess its solidification path.

Aiming at finding eco-friendly alternatives to the chromium-containing material, the same thermodynamic approach was used to assess the solidification path of binary, ternary or quaternary spinel systems (available in the aforementioned database) together with 66.4 wt% of MgO, giving rise to 154 distinct systems. This MgO content was selected because it is the same as that presented by the reference material (EMCA). To allow a better comparison among the simulated systems, they were ranked considering 5 key indicators, which will be presented later in this work. This ranking showed four systems with similar features to those presented by EMCA, thus, they were selected as the most promising and experimentally processed in a lab-scale arc melter (MAM-1, Edmund Buehler, Germany). To enable their electrofusion in this equipment, the raw materials presented in Tab. 1 were dispersed in a ball-milling with alumina balls for 2h and moulded into small (~ 1 cm^3) uniaxially-pressed (~ 60 MPa) pieces, avoiding powder asperion during electric arc opening.

Tab. 1: Composition of the four selected electrofused systems in a lab-scale arc melter.

Composition	MgO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	NiO	Ni ₂ O ₃
	wt%					
1	69.54	5.59	24.87	-	-	-
2	66.40	11.27	8.35	5.33	-	8.65
3	71.12	4.21	18.70	5.97	-	-
4	70.01	3.22	14.30	9.13	3.34	-

These pressed pieces were placed inside the electric arc melter and the melting process took place for ~ 90 seconds. Compared with the industrial electrofusion process, the lab-scale equipment imposes distinct processing conditions, such as much higher cooling rates (the samples cool down within seconds). Therefore, to bring them closer to the thermodynamic equilibrium, the as-fused samples were annealed for 5h at 1500 °C in a conventional electric heated furnace (Lindberg/Blue M, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). After that, the microstructure of the annealed samples was assessed by BSE/EDS and XRD (D8 Focus, Bruker, Germany).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Firstly, the microstructure of the commercially-available EMCA was analysed by BSE coupled with EDS (see Fig.1), highlighting that the aggregate is formed by a magnesium-oxide matrix

containing nodular precipitates with oxygen, magnesium, chromium, aluminium and iron as its main elements. Using the CALPHAD-based FactSage software, the mean composition of the two distinct regions was used as input for the thermodynamic calculation. The result indicated that the EMCA should be comprised of a complex spinel solid solution (spinel^{SS}) with the chemical formula $(\text{Mg}_{0.865}\text{Fe}_{0.135})(\text{Al}_{0.099}\text{Cr}_{0.877}\text{Fe}_{0.024})_2\text{O}_4$, surrounded by a periclase solid solution $[(\text{Mg}_{0.991}\text{Cr}_{0.006}\text{Fe}_{0.003})\text{O}]$ matrix. XRD analysis (not presented here) attested the formation of both phases, in line with previously reported works. Additionally, image analysis software was used to measure the mean diameter of the spinel precipitates, which was $15 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$.

Although the mineralogical composition and the microstructure of EMCA have already been reported in the literature, the mechanism that leads to the cracking behaviour seen in the microscopy (Fig.1) remains unclear. Thus, microcrack generation due to thermal expansion mismatch between distinct ceramic phases during the cooling process was considered. By using the approach proposed by Luchini *et al.*⁵ and considering the properties of the spinel^{SS} and periclase extracted from the literature (further information on these calculi is described in⁶), the minimum precipitate diameter (d_c) to generate microcracking in this system was calculated as $2.3 \mu\text{m}$. As the average spinel size measured in the EMCA ($15 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$) is considerably bigger than this value, microcracking due to thermal expansion mismatch is, indeed, expected. However, although the thermal expansion mismatch accounted for the highly cracked microstructure of the EMCA, it does not explain their crack orientation pattern, which plays a key role in the outstanding flexibility of this raw material. To assess the mechanism that leads to this oriented microcracking, EBSD analyses were conducted.

Fig. 1: Morphology and elementary mapping of the EMCA microstructure assessed by scanning electron microscopy coupled to energy dispersive spectroscopy. Extracted from [6] with Elsevier permission (n° 5573751435544).

Due to the unevenness of the surface, generated by the distinct hardness between the spinel and periclase (H_{Vickers} 's typically varying from 5.3 GPa to 8.6 GPa and 12 GPa to 16 GPa, respectively), no Kikuchi lines were detected for the former, however, the analysis could be conducted for the MgO matrix. Evaluating the obtained results (displayed in Fig. 2), the formation

of distinct MgO grains inside the aggregates was attested, giving rise to intergranular flaws, likely generated by solidification defects, at their interfaces (marked as F). Besides them, oriented cracks were observed within the MgO grains (marked as C). The post-processing software was used to determine their relative orientation, revealing a good fit with the $\{110\}$ family of crystallographic planes, which are the MgO slip planes, whereas $\{100\}$ are the cleavage ones. Additionally, the intersection among the oriented microcracks formed triangular slits (marked as S). These two features – cracks on slip planes instead of cleavage planes and the formation of triangular cracks – are in agreement with the cracking mechanism proposed by Zener and further described by Stroh⁷. According to these authors, crack nuclei are induced by a pile-up of edge dislocations that are halted at an obstacle, such as precipitates. In the case of MgO, non-homogeneous deformations (as those generated by thermal expansion mismatch) induce the pile-up of edge dislocations, resulting in crack nucleation at the $\{110\}$ family of planes and triangular slits at the crack intersection, similar to what was observed for the EMCA⁸.

Fig. 2: Microstructure of EMCA assessed by EBSD. The colours indicate the MgO orientation. Intergranular flaws, oriented cracks and triangular slits are highlighted as F, C and S, respectively. Extracted from [6] with Elsevier permission (n° 5573751435544).

Therefore, the microcrack orientation pattern established in the EMCA – and that gives rise to their flexibility – is attributed to the Zener-Stroh crack mechanism triggered by the stress generated due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the MgO and the complex spinel. Thus, the properties and geometry of the spinel precipitates play a key role in promoting such a structure as it will affect, (a) the thermal-induced stress level and, (b), act as dislocation barriers. At first sight, all these features seem to be feasible to obtain in a nontoxic and simpler system, such as a magnesia-rich MgO-Al₂O₃ composition. However, previous works showed that instead of spinel precipitates in a MgO matrix, this system presents the formation of periclase and spinel grains separately, which halts attaining preferentially oriented microcracks. Thus, to understand the role played by the chromite mineral on the formation of its microstructure, the solidification path of the EMCA and MgO-Al₂O₃ system were assessed by thermodynamics calculations carried out in the FactSage software. The solidification seen in Fig. 3 explains the distribution of phases in the EMCA (Fig.1), pointing out that the chromium addition plays a key role by enabling the formation of a MgO^{SS} at high temperatures, which exsolves a spinel^{SS} as the material cools down.

The results discussed so far pointed out the mechanism and key features responsible for the formation of the EMCA microstructure and, consequently, good thermomechanical properties. To do this, a system capable of forming a broad solid solution with MgO at high temperature, but exsolving a second phase presenting a lower thermal expansion coefficient, as internal precipitates with mean size higher than the critical value to induce fracture by thermal expansion mismatch is required to trigger the Zener-Stroh cracking mechanism, leading to highly oriented microcrack formation. This

intricate set of features explains why finding other compositions to replace the EMCA is so difficult, especially using the traditional selection paradigm. Therefore, the compositionally complex ceramic (CCC) selection approach was used to assess promising alternatives that could mimetize the EMCA but without containing chromium addition. The validated systems of FactSage 6.4 gave rise to a total of 154 compositions, which were ranked by taking 5 key indicators into account: (i) the periclase decay step; (ii) whether any gas was predicted to be generated up to 2800 °C; (iii) the solidification interval; (iv) the $\Delta\alpha$ between the periclase and the spinel formed; and (v) the temperature of the first liquid formation.

Fig. 3: EMCA (a) and M-A (b) solidification path assessed by FactSage. The drawings (c) presented a schematic representation of the microstructure at different temperatures. Extracted from [6] with Elsevier permission (n° 5573751435544).

According to these indicators and considering the reference values, 4 systems stood out as promising compositions to mimetize EMCA, as depicted in Tab. 2 (the values for all the 154 evaluated systems can be checked in⁶). At first, it is worth noticing that no Zn-containing system was selected, which is attributed to the high partial pressure of this element, resulting in gas formation at temperatures close to 2400 °C. Secondly, all selected compositions presented Fe additions, which was observed to display a similar role of Cr, also presenting a high solubility in periclase at high temperatures and able to exsolve a spinel structure during cooling.

Tab. 2: Indicator values for the EMCA and the four most promising compositions to mimetize it.

Composition	MgO decay (wt%)	Gas formation	Solidification interval (°C)	$\Delta\alpha$ (%)	First liquid formation (°C)
EMCA	40.4	No	450	42.9	2200
1	38.6	No	525	67.3	2200
2	34.0	No	550	37.8	2125
3	36.4	No	575	38.2	2100
4	34.5	No	550	38.2	2100

Although this computer-based selection method is valuable to guide the search for alternative eco-friendly compositions to replace the EMCA without performance losses, it must be experimentally validated to check its accuracy. Therefore, compositions 1 to 4 were processed in a laboratory-scale arc melter, which allows the production of small electrofused pieces (~ 1 cm³). Due to the processing conditions imposed by this equipment (especially high cooling rates), which are distinct from the industrial ones, the as-fused samples were annealed for 5 h at 1500 °C to bring them closer to the thermodynamic equilibrium. Aiming at assessing the mineralogical phases for each system, annealed samples were

grounded and the resulting powder was analyzed by XRD. Fig. 4 shows the X-ray diffractogram, highlighting the regions of 2 θ next to 35.5 ° and 43 °, where the most intense spinel and periclase peaks are located, respectively. By indexing the profiles, one can notice that just these two phases were identified, as the content of contaminants was lower. The highlighted peaks show significant changes for the spinel phase, remaining quite constant for periclase. This trend was expected as the systems were designed to present distinct spinel^{SS} compositions, whereas the periclase matrix is very similar, and is almost fully comprised by MgO. Moreover, quantitative mineralogical content indicated that all samples presented spinel content ranging from 34 wt% to 36 wt%, which is quite close to the values estimated using EDS data collected in the internal region of the grains of compositions 1 to 4 (see Fig. 5), especially considering the inherent uncertainty related to these experimental techniques.

Fig. 4: X-ray profile of the EMCA and compositions 1 to 4 after the annealing treatment. Extracted from [6] with Elsevier permission (n° 5573751435544).

However, the XRD analyses does not provide information regarding phase distribution and the presence of minor contaminating phases, thus the compositions were further analyzed by SEM in the BSE coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS), depicted in Fig. 5. Comparing the general morphological aspects similar trends could be observed for the four compositions:

- (i) Solidification defects were detected in the samples, which are assigned to the high solidification interval (> 500 °C) present by all compositions and the high cooling rates imposed by the lab-scale arc melter. In the industrial process, the compositions are produced in a block geometry that is subsequently broken and milled to give rise to the aggregates, which usually withdraws such solidification defects from the final microstructure.
- (ii) The microstructures presented some contamination mainly located at the periclase grain boundaries. The lighter color in the image indicates the presence of heavier elements in these regions, which were identified as calcium and tungsten that originated from the MgO raw material and the W-based electrode used in the melting process, respectively.
- (iii) All compositions underwent the formation of a periclase matrix with spinel precipitates. The EDS data coupled with thermodynamic calculations were used to assess the phase content of some selected regions showing that the grains are formed by ~ 40 wt% of spinel and ~ 60 wt% of periclase.

Fig. 5: Backscattered electron images of compositions 1, 2, 3 and 4. Extracted from [6] with Elsevier permission (n° 5573751435544).

However, obtaining a microstructure with MgO grains with spinel precipitates is a required but not sufficient condition to achieve a highly flexible material mimetizing the EMCA. Taking a closer look at the microstructure of compositions 1 to 4, the distinct morphology of the second phase stood out. For composition 1, a needle-like spinel structure was observed, whereas, for the other, nodular-like geometries were detected. Their sizes were assessed using image processing software (ImageJ, version 1.53t), which pointed out 0.9 μm , 1.4 μm and 2.5 μm as the mean equivalent diameter of the precipitates in compositions 2, 3 and 4, respectively. Not coincidentally, composition 4 presented the highest number of cracks, as bigger precipitates lead to higher stresses on the periclase matrix. Nevertheless, even for composition 4, the mean spinel size was considerably below the 15 μm presented by commercially produced EMCA, resulting in less crack generation than expected. In this sense, it is worth highlighting that the thermodynamic approach used in this analysis does not take kinetics into account. Thus, the larger spinel size observed in the EMCA (see Fig. 1) could be attributed to the much lower cooling rates applied in the industrial manufacturing of this raw material (electrofused blocks usually take close to 7 days to completely cool down) compared to that imposed by the laboratory-scale arc melter. To address such issues and understand whether the selection

method should also consider the temperature of spinel formation or if this variable could be neglected for industrially produced aggregates, electrofusing these compositions in larger scales would be needed and its on course.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, multiple electron-microscope-based techniques were used to assess EMCA microstructural features. BSE coupled with EDS highlighted that the aggregate comprises a magnesium-oxide matrix containing nodular-like precipitates. The mean size of the precipitated spinel was measured as $15 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$, which is above the critical diameter to induce microcracking due to thermal expansion mismatch in this system. However, such cracking is not randomly distributed and EBSD was used to assess its pattern, unveiling a good fit with the $\{110\}$ family of crystallographic planes. Therefore, the microcrack orientation pattern in the EMCA could be attributed to the Zener-Stroh crack mechanism triggered by the stress generated due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the MgO and the complex spinel. Based on this mechanism and with the aid of thermodynamic calculations, the concepts of designing compositionally complex ceramics were applied to find eco-friendly EMCA alternatives. From the 154 simulated systems, the four most promising compositions were experimentally produced using a laboratory-scale arc melter and characterized by XRD and BSE/EDS. Although kinetics aspects still must be addressed, Cr-free EMCA-inspired microstructures were obtained, highlighting that this design approach can be used to support the development of novel raw-material that can better merge performance, cost and eco-friendliness.

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REFERENCES

- Wang, E., Luo, C., Chen, J. & Hou, X. High-performance chromite by structure stabilization treatment. *J. Iron Steel Res. Int.* **27**, 169–179 (2020).
- Xu, T. *et al.* Corrosion mechanisms of magnesia-chrome refractories in copper slag and concurrent formation of hexavalent chromium. *J. Alloys Compd.* **786**, 306–313 (2019).
- Horckmans, L., Nielsen, P., Dierckx, P. & Ducastel, A. Recycling of refractory bricks used in basic steelmaking: a review. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **140**, 297–304 (2019).
- Wright, A. J. *et al.* From high-entropy ceramics to compositionally-complex ceramics: a case study of fluorite oxides. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* **40**, 2120–2129 (2020).
- Luchini, B., Sciuti, V. F., Angélico, R. A., Canto, R. B. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Critical inclusion size prediction in refractory ceramics via finite element simulations. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* **37**, 315–321 (2017).
- Borges, O. H., Coury, F. G., Mucbe, D. N. F. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Eco-friendly design of complex refractory aggregates as alternatives to the magnesia-chromite ones. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (2023) doi:10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2023.06.023.
- Stroh, A. N. The formation of cracks as a result of plastic flow. *Proc. R. Soc. London. Ser. A. Math. Phys. Sci.* **223**, 404–414 (1954).
- Armstrong, R. W. Dislocation pile-ups: from $\{110\}$ cracking in MgO to model strength evaluations. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **409**, 24–31 (2005).